

FABRICATION OF WASTE ENGINE OIL BURNER: TRENDS AND CHALLENGES IN NIGERIAN POTTERY INDUSTRY

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Abstract

In 2006, the waste oil burner; fabricated by the researcher under gone testing at the University of Benin. From the wealth of this experimental work, it is obvious that: Waste oil when used with the fabricated burner is very viable. Waste oil firing attracts less overhead cost compared to other fuel types. Possibilities of achieving unique surface finishing effect are more assuring. This research is significant in that it has lent credence and support to the issue of waste to wealth. Waste Oil Burner the principal necessity for this project was borne out of the desire to revive the declining pottery practice in the various ceramic centres in Nigeria. Especially against the backdrop of energy crisis which often present some problems in terms of production cost. And to determining the possibilities of using locally fabricated burner for firing ceramic wares. This is with the sole aim of finding lasting alternative to other liquid fuels as a means of firing ceramic wares. After conducting series of test on the fabricated burner, recorded results have been positive. The project shall be referred to as Eweka Burner in this presentation.

Introduction

In Nigeria, the absence of local processing plants for raw materials and fabrication of needed machinery were major challenges experienced by potters. The high import duties on equipments, processed imported raw materials combined with absence of energy for powering machinery in the industry are accountable for the slow pace of development of the local ceramic industry.

The trends and development in the fabrication of reliable burner for firing bisque and glaze wares has been very slow; not much has been done after Yusuff experiment in Zaria in the 90s. It was observed in the course of this research that practicing artist and studio potters have consistently suffered setbacks due to the constant hike in the prices of petroleum products, such as kerosene, diesel and gas, the constant electric power outage had made matters worse. The cost of procuring fuel whether solid or liquid, poses a challenge for small-

scale ceramic industries including schools and colleges that offer ceramic courses.

The purpose of the project was to address those problems that are common to potters in the course of firing their wares. Prominent among which was to find a relatively affordable source of liquid fuel to operate the fabricated burner for firing of pottery wares among practicing potters in Nigeria. The University of Benin experiment in 2006 the burner type fabricated utilized waste oil as fuel. The designed burner haven been tested will serve as a prototype for potters desiring such an apparatus for the firing of their products.

There are various types of fuel available for firing ceramics wares which are grouped into three main divisions- solid, liquid and gas: The liquids are kerosene, diesel, petrol and oil; while the solid are wood, sawdust and coal and the third group is gas sold in bottles

as liquefied gas. The most affordable of all these fuel types are the waste oil and sawdust. However, sawdust and firewood are more cumbersome and may require a lot of storage space. Waste engine oil may be collected from mechanic and machines repair centers across the metropolises at little or no cost, which is then stored in plastic cans for use. Most importantly, the measure is minimal in terms of fire hazards to the Potter.

Revising the Trends and Challenges

The researcher has observed that the pottery tradition in Nigeria is on the decline. In the opinion of the researcher the decline could be due to setbacks, suffered by practicing potters. Such as constant hike in the prices of petroleum products: such as kerosene; diesel and gas; and the constant electric power failure. This has made the cost of thermal processing of ceramics increasingly difficult. This difficulty has brought about declining interest in setting up ceramics studios and cottage ceramics industries.

The project is significant because, the sourcing of cheaper and affordable fuel using waste fuel will help to stimulate interest in students, professional and other individuals towards experimentation and production purpose in the ceramic industry. The device Eweka Burner is unique in the sense that the problems of clogging, blockage of nozzle and nipple were eliminated.

Review of Studio Practice and Knowledge

In the studies carried out by Yusuf (1990), he supported Considine's (1976, p. 49) view that, "a burner is a principal component of combustion and applied to burning fuel with air to generate heat". As it applies to the subject of discussion, Eweka Burner is a mechanical device with which fuel mixed with air under controlled conditions is used for lighting flames and heating purposes. Encyclopedia Britannica (2008) reviewed that, "in most burners oil is supplied under pressure to an atomizing nozzle to produce a fire spray, to which air is added by a motor-driven fan". This view fully explained

the principle of the operation of the fabricated device to support optimum combustion. Barnett, (2008) elicits as follows:

Fire results from a rapid chemical reaction between a fuel, such as wood or gasoline, and oxygen. Reactions that involve oxygen and other elements are called oxidation reactions. Chemists use the word combustion to refer to the oxidation reaction that produces fire. Combustion generates light, heat, gases, and soot.

Most practicing potters in the country will agree with the view, that the basic kiln design is the same no matter the type of fuel used, Nelson, (1960, p.273) states that "perhaps the most drastic change in kiln design was caused by the development of a new source of power - electricity". The operation of an electric kiln needs no chimney or fuel lines. And it is thought as comparatively portable. Rhodes (1973, p.238) opines that "many situations called for electric kiln". He further states that "the operations of electric are clear, compact and odorless" (ibid). This entire attribute, notwithstanding, has its shortcomings within the context of Small and medium scale in Nigeria; where power failure is constantly recorded.

Liquefied petroleum gas are bottled in kilograms per weight for sale to end-users, these are the 12.5 kg, 25 kg and 50 kg categories. Rhodes (ibid) stated that "bottled gas (liquefied bottled gas) gives result in pottery firing in every way identifiably with natural gas". He noted further that "bottled gas is more expensive and requires special equipment for storage and combustion"(ibid). In spite of the bottled advantages accruing from the use of bottled gas, its supply is not regular and it is also very expensive in Nigeria.

The fabrication of Eweka Burner is a welcome development because it undermined the fear raised by Rhodes (ibid) that 'oil burners', however, are more complex more expensive, and subject to mechanical failure than gas burner has been addressed by the success of this project. Interestingly, the technology associated with the fabricated oil burner has been simplified in relation its operation for ceramic firing in the Kiln.

Methodology/Studio Practice

Working sketches relevant to the fabrication were made to specification which serves as guide for the actual fabricated burner.

The second step was the drawings of the complete visual illustration of the burner and accessories. In the fabrication of *Eweka* burner, steel pipe was the preference for the project. The selection of this variety of pipe was based on its tendency to withstand melting during firing process inside the burner port of the ceramic kiln. All the different parts forming the burner were cut to various dimensions as indicated in the prepared sketches. All the different parts were formed together using the electric welding. The fabricated burners were then fitted with a twelve-voltage fan, powered by a car battery. Accessories: The following accessories complimented the performance of the fabrication. Battery: The burner was fixed with a 12 v. amp car fan; the energy needed to make it function was imported from a 12volt sixty-amp car battery to motorize the fan. Battery charging equipment: This device was used to replace the expended battery energy in order to prolong its life span for subsequent firing operations, (See Plate I). Launch Pad: The fabricated burner was then seated on a constructed metal table as a launch pad for effective manipulation during firing activities. (Plate II).

Gravity Pad: The supply of fuel to the burner was based on the principle of gravity. This was achieved by placing the gravity pad three feet high above the burner port upon which the fuel tank was mounted for the firing operation (Plate III). Fuel tank: The mounted tank was made out of a plastic paint container fitted with a ball-joint-valve which, was used to regulate the flow of fuel supplied to the burner for firing operation see (Plate III).

Sizeable fuel hose: The fuel tank was linked to the burner by means of a sizeable hose, which was connected directly from the control valve of the tank, delivering fuel to the nipple of the burner where it is mixed with air for proper combustion.

Testing Out:

The trial test aimed at finding out the efficiency of the fabricated burner using waste engine oil as fuel. Having collected the waste engine from in and around the Benin metropolis, the collected waste was oil was then passed through a 60 inch mesh to remove dirt so as to allow a free flow of oil through the fuel line to the burner. The kiln was then preheated for about three hours by burning wood chips at the burner port to allow for proper atomization. When the burner was introduced to the port for proper combustion, oil was supplied at slow rate to the burner with air supply reduced by half speed to allow for prolong pre-heating to safeguard the wares loaded inside the kiln.

As the internal temperature of the kiln rose slightly above 500°C, the valve controlling the fuel line was open up to allow more supply of oil followed by an increase in air supply this resulted into a full blast. The fuel tank was occasionally refilled to maintain maximum fuel supply to the burner. This sequence was repeated throughout the firing sessions in 2006 and 2007 for the bisque, glazed wares of Undergraduate and Masters Student at the University of Benin by the researcher.

Studio Note/Result:

There have always been uninterrupted firing, without the usual clogging, backfiring and blocking of the burner nozzle associated with the coil burner. At full atomization the flame produced in the burner port is clear, smooth similar to gas burner. This is as a result of adequate supply of air from the large nozzle of the burner.

In spite of thick smoke produced at some point in course of the firing, the interior of the Kiln remained clean without deposits of soot on the pottery wares being fired. The burner was efficiently employed for reduction and oxidation firing with astonishing result on glazed wares. The use waste engine oil does not have negative impact on bisque and glazed wares. From further explorative firing with the burner, it was found out that other liquid fuel types with the exception of petrol fired well. Photograph of bisque and glazed from the experiments are in appendix I.

Conclusion

Potentials of firing bisque at 800°C to 960°C temperature attained 1050°C while gloss and 1250°C respectively. Firing time proved marked difference on the surface quality on

followed by a drastic reduction on the smoke produced. At the attainment of high temperature, the Kiln chamber had a clear atmosphere even when smoke is introduced; it is expelled through the chimney. To replicate the entire project will attract modest cost in terms of fuel, burner construction and operation.

Fig. 1: Burner casing with dimensions

Keys:

- 1. Fuel Tank
- 2. Fuel Line
- 3. Burner Nozzle
- 4. Fan
- 5. Gravity Pad
- 6. Launch Pad.

Plate II: Fabricated Burner in action seated on constructed metal stand

Plate III: Fuel can on an elevated height using the principle of gravity to supply fuel to the Burner

s in Nigerian Pottery Industry

Plate IV: Burner connected by means of a sizeable hose to the fuel tank

Plate V: Complete **fabricated burner**

Plate VI: Component part of the fabricated burner

Visual Outcomes of the Experiment for Bisque and Glazed Pottery,

Table I: Cost analysis of the price fuel available to potters in Nigeria within the period, January 2006 to September 2008

S/N	Fuel Type	Naira/Litre	Quantity/Litre
1	Kerosene	N50	50
2	Diesel	N135	50
3	Gas	N130	50(kg)
4	Waste Oil	N10	50

Definitions of Special Terms

Kiln - A furnace made up of refractory clay material for the firing of ceramic products.

Launch Pad - A stand constructed for the sitting of the burning device during firing process. —

Nipple - Opening six inches away from the nozzle of the burner, an inlet for the droplet of oil into the burner.

Gravity pad - An elevated platform which the fuel bucket is place to allow flow of fuel through the fuel nozzle by the force of gravity.

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